

**OAEBUDT Rulebook
Community
Consultation
Results
August 2023 -
March 2024**

Authors

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Executive Summary

After [initial community consultations](#) from January to June 2023 explored issues related to open access (OA) book usage data exchange within an international data space (IDS), initial data exchange principles were drafted in an [April 2023 in-person workshop](#). Those principles were further developed into a participant rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) by a “Rulebook Task Team” (expert working group) informed by the community consultations described in this document. From August 2023 through March 2024, the collection of such community feedback was facilitated through online focus groups and web forms. The results of these methods are analyzed and documented herein to inform the *OA Book Usage Data Exchange and Stewardship Rulebook [version 0.0](#)*. For transparency, provided feedback has been transcribed without the correction of spelling or typos.

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August-November 2023 | Rulebook content development Web-form Consultation (3 submissions)

Global stakeholders were invited to iteratively provide feedback as the Rulebook Task Team developed draft rulebook language. As the Rulebook Task Team completed a set of principles or terms for review, a web form based consultation was launched to present the draft language to the community and collect asynchronous feedback. Consultations were advertised via the OAEBUDT listserv and social media. The three rounds of consultation directly informed the drafting of rulebook language; topics addressed during this rulebook content development phase spanned usage data quality and sensitivity, privacy, transparency, community governance, security, and data reuse. (Note: A fourth consultation invited public comment on the full Rulebook draft (See [below](#).) All submissions were anonymous and did not collect respondents' email or IP addresses. Despite robust advertising and amplification of social media through partner networks, only 3 submissions were received during the content development phase. This feedback was informative, constituting suggestions on rephrasing, visual changes and matrix definition considerations. It was shared back with the Rulebook Task Team and where possible, implemented into the draft Rulebook. Feedback collected for each web form is summarized below.

Web Form 1 - Data Provider Participation Terms (30 Aug - 15 Sep 2023, 1 response)

In the first web form, feedback was sought on principles drafted to ensure trust in the usage data providers participating in the OAEBUDT. The principles shared are listed below together with the comments received.

1. To establish that an organization is a CREDIBLE ORGANIZATION that can be held accountable for the data it provides, a Data Provider must:
 - (1a) be a recognized, legally incorporated organization in any country, including public institutions, corporations, and not-for-profit organizations
 - (1b) provide a valid Tax Identification Number (TIN) or other documentation to establish their legal authority

Feedback:

- These two requirements seem utterly reasonable.

2. To establish that an organization is TRUSTED TO EXCHANGE DATA, a Data Provider must:
 - (2a.) be a responsible member of the OA Book Usage Data Trust in good membership standing (not inactive or on probation)
 - (2b.) meet the requirements of Data Providers set forth by the OA Book Usage Data Trust in this Rulebook and associated participation terms, conditions, and legal agreements
 - (2c.) if an organization is actively preparing to exchange data as a "Data Provider Member" of the Data Trust but does not yet meet the requirements of Data Providers, the organization may formally affiliate with the Data Trust as a "Partner" organization

Feedback:

- 2c might be reframed with an OR statement—that they are a Data Provider Member OR actively preparing...

3. To establish that an organization maintains ACTIVE RESPONSIBILITY for the usage data it makes available to others, a Data Provider must:
- (3a.) manage the platform, service, repository, or webpage that generated the usage data being provided through the OA Book Usage Data Trust
 - (3b.) accept responsibility for the QUALITY of all usage data they provide through the OA Usage Data Trust; quality is defined across multiple dimensions such as: accuracy, granularity, consistency, regularity
 - (3c.) if an issue is reported related to the QUALITY of the usage data exchanged by the Data Provider, the Data Provider agrees to investigate and provide a response to the issue

Feedback:

- These all seem reasonable. Perhaps remove the color after “such as” in 3b?

4. To establish that an organization holds and maintains the LEGAL AUTHORITY to distribute its usage data to others, a Data Provider must:
- (4a.) have the LEGAL AUTHORITY to make usage data available for processing or specific third party use through the OA Usage Data Trust
 - (4b.) provide NOTIFICATION and obtain the necessary CONSENT as is legally required prior to making usage data available for processing or specific third party use through the OA Book Usage Data Trust

Feedback:

- This all seems reasonable.

Web Form 2 - Data Quality Disclosures (21 Sep - 15 Oct 2023, 2 responses)

In the second consultation, feedback was sought on principles drafted to ensure trust in the disclosures about the data being made available in the OAEBUDT. Two statements and a data quality matrix of data quality trust indicator levels were presented, generating feedback that was taken back to the Rulebook Task Team.

- To establish that an organization will be TRANSPARENT about the usage data it makes available to others, a Data Provider must:
- a. describe the process by which the usage data was created
 - b. provide a description of usage data provenance, to allow others to understand who was involved in the creation and processing of usage data prior to it being made available to the OA Book Usage Data Trust
 - c. provide metadata for the usage data that it believes to be accurate, including at a minimum: {list to be determined}
 - d. describe all transformations or processing conducted on the usage data prior to making it available through the Data Trust (noting algorithms, code, or standards that were applied where applicable, and whether such algorithms, code or standards are proprietary or available for open review).

Feedback:

- I agree with these statements.
- Transparency in data collection should at minimum require information about (a) the sampling frame (the rules determining what units of measurement are potentially reachable for measurement) (b) the selection mechanism (how are units selected from within the overall frame for measurement) (c) the measures applied (d) post-processing of the responses, (e) the period of measurement, (f) non-response rates

To support diverse, inclusive participation in the Data Trust from a variety of data providers, distinct data quality levels will support:

- broad organization-to-organization data exchange (Level I), and
- standards-compliant values processed from data sourced from multiple platforms (Level II)

Data Providers will be asked to describe the data they make available to help data users understand the usage data they receive. To inform this data quality notification process and technical security and access requirements, the following matrix of definitions has been developed to help data providers describe the state of their usage data in terms of:

- "Item-Level" Data Accuracy,
- "Item-Level" Data Generation Transparency,
- "Item-level" Data Delivery Reliability, and
- "Item-Level" Data Frequency.

Data Providers will be asked to select the best fit description of the state of their usage data for each data quality indicator.

Feedback:

- I agree with these definitions and statements as well!
- Not clear what these data quality levels are. More important, whatever the level of quality, data should be supplied with honest measures of uncertainty and accuracy.

Trust level headings will be reflected in the Data Rulebook as presented in the matrix below.

	Low Trust	Some Trust	Most Trust
OAEBU "Item-Level" Data Accuracy	Not conformant to any published, community standard; e.g. Non-COUNTER Compliant	Conformant or self-certified as compliant to an industry standard; e.g. COUNTER conformance for past or current version of the COUNTER Code of Practice	Third-party certified compliance with a published community standard; e.g. COUNTER Compliance for the Current Code of Practice, as evidenced by listing in https://registry.projectcounter.org/
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Generation Transparency	Ad hoc, standard, or common proprietary usage data processing software with no description of data generation method	Standard or common proprietary usage data processing software and basic description on the data generation method	Open source usage data processing software & full description on the data generation method
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Delivery Reliability	Irregular availability or variance in the reporting periods over time	Data delivered with some exceptions	Data delivered on time without exceptions
OAEBU "Item-level" Data Frequency	Irregular data delivery frequency	Regular metric publication on at least a monthly frequency	On-demand metric exchange

Comment on this matrix below the image.

Feedback:

- I wonder if "Data Accuracy" could be "Data Credibility" — when I hear "Accuracy", I think more about the information of the data as accurate (i.e. are ISSNs matched with the correct title, is there no duplicates, missing data pieces, etc.). When I hear "credibility", I'm thinking reputable or whether or not it's undergone a "checks and balances" system.
- This chart fundamentally confuses dimensions of reliability, completeness comparability/standardization, accuracy, granularity, and trustworthiness. It would be better to separate these out. For example -- trustworthiness (e.g. justified belief that the data was actually generated by the process as stated by the publisher) is reinforced through certification, process transparency (e.g. open data), provenance tracking, fixity tracking, replication, and auditing. Comparability is supported by measures defined in reference to a public standard, quantitative measures of uncertainty, synchronization (or standardization) of measurement time periods, compatibility of sampling frame and selection mechanism, and sufficient information to link observed units (or well-defined groups).

Please note anything else you'd like to share for consideration.

Feedback:

- A list of data definitions (maybe a "Data Dictionary" if you will) for referencing. This may be something that already lumps under one of the points above, but it ideally could be presented as an Appendix of some sort.

Web Form 3 - Data Sensitivity (31 Oct - 15 Nov 2023, no responses)

The third consultation on data exchange principles presented draft language from the Task Team on allowable use and use restrictions for specific data elements that could be exchanged via the OAEBUDT. These principles could inform which data licenses will be made available to both the usage data providers wishing to share their data via the OAEBUDT IDS and usage data recipients wishing to access data via the OAEBUDT IDS.

Despite significant outreach, no responses were received to this consultation. However, the decision was made to leverage planned virtual focus groups ([see below](#)) to generate feedback on these topics.

15 November 2023 | Online Focus Groups (14 participants)

Two focus groups were organized on the 15th of November (7.30 AM and 2 PM UTC) to allow for participation in different time zones. Participants were presented with language developed by the Rulebook Task Team in PowerPoint slides with a narrative description provided by Community Manager Rabar. After a set of text was presented, responses were requested using the tool Mentimeter, allowing individuals to contribute ideas via their computing or mobile device. Rabar also facilitated discussion to clarify key points. The same set of 15 questions were presented to each focus group, sometimes generating multiple responses from participants. (Table 1).

Across both focus group sessions, 14 individuals participated representing libraries, university presses, publishers and service/platform providers from Europe, Canada, the US, and Africa.

Image 1. Focus Groups Participants' Locations and Stakeholder Types

Table 1: November 2023 Focus Group Questions and Response Count

Question	Number of respondents	Number of responses
Terms and Conditions of Participation		
Q1. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Providers?	11	15
Q2. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Recipients?	6	8
Data Disclosures		
Q3. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Accuracy Trust Levels?	5	9
Q4. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Generation Transparency Trust Levels?	5	5
Q5. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Delivery Reliability Trust Levels?	5	5
Q6. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Frequency Trust Levels?	3	3
Q7. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Granularity Trust Levels?	5	7
Q8. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Consistency Trust Levels?	3	5
Data Sensitivity, Openness, and Related Use or Reuse Limitations		
Q9. Book Metadata - Do you have any comments or concerns?	10	10
Q10. Global Usage Data - Do you have any comments or concerns?	10	10
Q11. Organization-Specific Usage Data - Do you have any comments or concerns?	7	7
Q12. Individual-Specific OA Book Usage Data - Do you have any comments or concerns?	10	11
Q13. Book Citation Data - Do you have any comments or concerns?	9	10
Q14. OA Book Reader Engagement - Behavioral Data - Do you have any comments or concerns?	10	10
Q15. Usage Benchmarking Data - Do you have any comments or concerns?	8	9

The feedback provided at both focus groups is combined below to provide an overall view of feedback per topic. Feedback is grouped by the relevant rulebook section and focus group question.

Data Provider Terms and Conditions

Q1. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Providers?

Question framing asked participants to consider if anything was missing from the presented text, or if the terms presented would present an obstacle, in the respondents' opinion, to data space participation for organizations that would provide usage data (Data Providers). The feedback provided spanned compliance monitoring, enforcement, and transparency in how organizations provide and describe their data.

Such feedback informed the development of the Rulebook 0.0 version¹ *SECTION II, Part I. Roles in a Scalable International Data Space (IDS) to Interconnect Data Providers and Data Recipients, and Part II. Disclosures to Foster Book Usage Data Quality and Trust*. Provided comments confirmed what had already been flagged as the most important aspect for organizations when participating in the OAEBUDT data space: trust.

The image shows a collection of comment cards arranged in a grid-like fashion within a rounded rectangular frame. The cards contain various feedback points related to data provider terms and conditions. The comments are as follows:

- No, the main concerns are covered
- No
- The timely provision of usage data in a useful dashboard
- Important that the providers are trusting enough to be open about their data.
- Will policy compliance be compulsory? This will help everyone re universal standards in use
- What are the best practices used to validate and maintain data accuracy?
- I am not sure what the added value would be, given the cost structures and process complexities
- The right to be forgotten: the organization must offer a way for people to be removed from the data base
- These principles are admirable. I'm unclear about who will be monitoring and "enforcing" them, and the time commitment involved in doing so seems very large.
- Maybe something about working within agreed standards or formats?
- No comments on this one

Comments on Data Provider Related Drafted Principles

¹ Drummond, C., Watson, J., Mounier, P., Elwell, J., Stern, N., Lenahan, J., Legre, Y., & Tsiavos, P. (2024). Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) (Version 0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11163158>

Data Recipient Terms and Conditions

Q2. *Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Recipients?*

Community input spanned use guidelines for accessed data, and questions about the IDS approach, signaling that much education was still needed to raise awareness of how the IDS could complement existing usage data supply chains.

The image shows a collection of comment boxes from community members regarding data recipient terms and conditions. The comments are as follows:

- There will be usage guidelines? Seems reasonable
- I wonder what the size of the market is in terms of data repositories and use cases
- Would guidelines for what constitutes misuse be made clear, and consequences for misuse Will Data Space understand the possibly unique use-cases in the scholarly comm ecosystem?
- What about the interfaces with existing initiatives such as Nakala?
- Some examples of Data Recipients? Publishers, then? As a medium sized publisher we can currently only receive excel from aggregators. We dont receive xml type feeds, so how would that work?

Comments on Data Recipient Related Drafted Principles

Concerns related to the monitoring of Data Recipients compliance with data usage exchange guidelines, were addressed by the Rulebook 0.0 version² in *SECTION II, Part III. Usage Data Sharing and Use Policies, Part IV. Accountability Mechanisms.*

Usage Data Disclosure Requirements

Q3. *Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Accuracy Trust Levels?*

To support metadata disclosures about the usage data being exchanged. Data Providers will describe their data within the OAEBUDT in a standardized way. Six dimensions of item-level usage data quality identified by the Rulebook Task Team (data generation, accuracy, transparency, reliability, frequency, granularity, and consistency) were presented to participants. For each indicator, three trust-level descriptions generated by the Task Team were presented, one for low trust, one for some trust, and one for most trust. Participants were invited to suggest additions or other comments. Feedback received for each Open Access Ebook Usage (OAEBU) data quality dimension is summarized below.

² Drummond, C., Watson, J., Mounier, P., Elwell, J., Stern, N., Lenahan, J., Legre, Y., & Tsiavos, P. (2024). Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) (Version 0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11163158>

OAEBU Data Quality Dimension 1: Data Generation Transparency

Q4. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Generation Transparency Trust Levels?

Low Trust	Some Trust	Most Trust
Ad hoc, standard, or common proprietary usage data processing software with no description of data generation method	Standard or common proprietary usage data processing software and basic description on the data generation method	Open source usage data processing software & full description on the data generation method

Comments:

- The practicability of this needs to be demonstrated
- These seem reasonable
- An example of open source software you mentioned for the most trust case?
- What are the best practices used to validate and maintain data generation in complex datasets?
- It would help if examples re given in the medium and top trust column.

OAEBU Data Quality Dimension 2: Data Accuracy

Q3. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Accuracy Trust Levels?

Low Trust	Some Trust	Most Trust
Not conformant to any published, community standard; e.g. Non-COUNTER Compliant	Conformant or self-certified as compliant to an industry standard; e.g. COUNTER conformance for past or current version of the COUNTER Code of Practice	Third-party certified compliance with a published community standard; e.g. COUNTER Compliance for the Current Code of Practice, as evidenced by listing in https://registry.projectcounter.org/

Comments:

- No
- Is it going to be self certified by data providers?
- The existing trust levels are industry standard
- Sounds reasonable to me too
- Sounds reasonable. With the non-conformant bit, would that be where it's not in the right format? Or data missing? Or all and any of that?
- Sounds good
- It would be good to know about examples of the sort of things that are likely to be merged
- If we were looking to find a new standard aside from COUNTER, how would we go about this? Creating a new community standard means it might take a while to be trusted.
- Sounds reasonable.

OAEBU Data Quality Dimension 3: Data Delivery Reliability

Q5. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Delivery Reliability Trust Levels?

Low Trust	Some Trust	Most Trust
Irregular availability or variance in the reporting periods over time	Data delivered with some exceptions	Data delivered on time without exceptions

Comments:

- Wondered about rationale for 3 levels vs 2: reliable vs less reliable
- Looks good to me
- No
- Who assesses the data delivery reliability trust level?
- Maybe the level of expectations needs to be lowered proactively

OAEBU Data Quality Dimension 4: Data Frequency

Q6. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Frequency Trust Levels?

Low Trust	Some Trust	Most Trust
Irregular data delivery frequency	Regular metric publication on at least a monthly frequency	On-demand metric exchange

Comments:

- This might also need to be checked for viability
- The “some trust” category adds generation transparency to the delivery of un-merged data. Is it intentional?
- No

OAEBU Data Quality Dimension 5: Data Granularity

Q7. Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Granularity Trust Levels?

Low Trust	Some Trust	Most Trust
When all usage data is merged into one single number without the ability to check the different elements of the data or how the data was calculated	Deliver usage data without merging it and providing data generation transparency	Data sources are fully available and include GDPR compliant raw web analytics

Comments:

- That can be challenging
- One single number appears very problematic, should this be explicitly listed as discouraged
- This adds data generation transparency to un-merged usage data, but that is not explicit in the low- or most- trust categories. Is that intentional?
- Be good to know what sort of things would be likely to be merged into a single figure
- No
- All aspects can be overly unrealistic to deliver
- What is the context for the two year timeline?

OAEBU Data Quality Dimension 6: Data Consistency

Q8. *Is there anything you would like to add regarding Data Consistency Trust Levels?*

Low Trust	Some Trust	Most Trust
<p><u>Multiple</u> generation methods used over the past year for the same type of data and/or the change of method <u>is not declared</u></p>	<p><u>No more than 2</u> generation methods used to generate the same type of data over the past two years and the change of method <u>is declared</u></p>	<p><u>Consistent</u> generation method used for data for <u>more than two years</u> and the change of method is due to complying with a published, community standard; e.g. COUNTER Compliance</p>

Comments:

- Consistent time horizons for Low Trust and Some Trust might be desirable?
- Looks good, no questions on this one
- I can't see the need for tight controls on any of this (am I being naive?) so I agree with it being as open as legally possible
- I wonder if there are examples of data providers already compliant with these criteria and sharing data openly
- All looks fine to be as open as legally possible

Responses generally agreed that these principles are reasonable and similar to some that already exist - i.e. they would not be new to the community. Questions about self-certification and who conducts the checks were raised.

Data Sensitivity, Openness, and Related Use or Reuse Limitations

An overview of potential book usage related data elements identified by the Rulebook Task Team was presented, noting that they could eventually be exchanged in the data space between Data Providers and Data Recipients. Participants were shown the Task Teams initial suggestions on whether exchange of each sensitive data type could be treated as "As open as legally possible" or "Most Controlled" due to ethical and legal concerns arising from high legal, ethical, or personal risk. Participants were asked to provide comments and/or concerns related to the level of openness or control suggested by the Task Team. Seven types of data were presented, spanning traditional bibliometrics and reading behaviors: 1) book metadata, 2) global usage data, 3) organization-specific usage data, 4) individual-specific usage data, 5) book citation data, 6) reader-engagement data, and 7) usage benchmarking data. Feedback is summarized below.

<p>Data Category 1: OA book metadata Item-level open bibliographic metadata Item-level ONIX records</p>	
<p>As open as legally possible</p>	<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No • Yes, I agree • None • Collaborations with metadata providers, is that possible? • I cant think of any risks or why more control would be needed • This is complex technically • Agree • Agree • The data should be as open as possible • Agree with the framework
<p>Data Category 2: Global usage data elements Usage event data associated with specific countries or regions Usage event data associated with specific market segments, disciplines, or domains</p>	
<p>As open as legally possible</p>	<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't see issues here either • Agree, no issues with this • Agree that this is reasonable • As open as legally possible sounds fine here too • This can be difficult to manage vis a vis client groups • No :) • Agree • As open as legally possible • No
<p>Data Category 3: Organization-specific usage data elements Usage event data for specific publishers Usage event data for specific institutions (e.g. universities, libraries, platforms)</p>	
<p>As open as legally possible</p>	<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree for the first point, not sure how happy libraries/universities would be with their usage data being open to others outside of the publisher • Not sure if feasible • Agree • This seems like an are where an opt-in or opt-out policy might be considered? • Institutions should get able to choose, for teers of openness • No • Agree

<p>Data Category 4: Individual-specific usage data elements Individual events of usage at an individual IP address level of detail Individual events of usage at an individual person (i.e. unique identifier - i.e. ORCID, screen name, etc.) level of detail Unprocessed web page log files for unique items as defined per COUNTER COP 5.1.6.1 as: “text files representing individual HTTP requests, including the user host name or IP address, the date and time of the request, the requested file name, the HTTP response status and size, the referring URL and the browser information.”</p>	
<p>High legal, ethical, or personal risk</p> <p>Most controlled</p>	<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Red flag territory • Agree, this should be most controlled • I agree-most controlled across all three types • Agree it should be most controlled • Agree • Agreed • Agree • Thumbs up! • It would set some members or scholars more at ease if there is flexibility • Agree • Different levels of openness should be made possible, so data can move or be in different categories
<p>Data Category 5: Book citation data elements News or social media citation of an item-level work Educational - syllabi or publication citation of an item-level work Research - patent or publication citation of an item-level work Public citation of an item-level work (e.g. Crossref Events Data)</p>	
<p>As open as legally possible</p>	<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This will complete with existing offers on the market • Agree with this too, this is the kind of thing our authors are very interested in • Authors definitely want to know this. • The first, yes. The second, it depends whether you can identify the reader or not. If not, then less need for it to be so controlled • Agree - A lot of this is openly available, why apply a more restrictive framework • Agree this should be included but a lot of this information can be found elsewhere already • As open as possible • Agree • As open as possible! • Agree

<p>Data Category 6: OA book reader engagement-behavioral data elements Page annotation activity Duration and/or timestamps related to viewing activity</p>	
<p>High legal, ethical, or personal risk Most controlled</p>	<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreed • Technically challenging, privacy concern is paramount • I agree the first should be controlled data but I don't see why duration would need to be • Yes, agreed • Is some of the duration activity patterns covered in COUNTER? • The first yes, the second, it depends whether the reader can be identified. If not, less need for it to be so tightly controlled • Reader can choose/optional • Yes, this needs to be protected, but will probably also be the most asked for information. • Agreed • To what extent could this be anonymized? And therefor shareable?
<p>Data Category 7: Usage benchmarking data elements Benchmarked average usage value calculated for items within standard categories (e.g. BISAC subject codes)</p>	
<p>As open as legally possible</p>	<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree • Likely demands extra labor inputs • Agreed • Yes • This is the USP for the OAEBUDT, in my opinion, so important to keep it as open as possible, as closed as necessary. • Agree • Agree • Agree • Agree

The majority of the participants agreed with the suggested openness or control needed for the different data elements. The focus groups' results were shared with the dedicated Rulebook Task Team and adopted into the Rulebook in line with the comments received.

Full Draft Rulebook Consultation (February - March 2024, 4 participants)

Web Form 4 - Rulebook Draft Community Consultation (15 Feb - 7 Mar 2024, 4 responses)

A final web form sought community feedback on the full rulebook draft document prior to publication. After asking for respondent geographical location, the web form requested feedback on rulebook content, rulebook applicability, and trust in the data exchange.

Rulebook Content

Five-point Likert scale questions asked respondents to evaluate the document's clarity. Free text allowed respondents to suggest additions or changes. Table 2 reflects the feedback received.

Table 2: Rulebook Draft Feedback

Questions	Answers												
<p>Are there any key aspects that you think are missing or not adequately covered in the rulebook?</p> <p>If yes, please provide feedback on which ones.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I suggest adding the following paragraph to SECTION I OAEBUDT-IDS PARTICIPANT RULEBOOK OVERVIEW: "A Data Space embodies the idea of sharing data without centralized storage, ensuring that data remains at its original source and is only shared when needed." 2- Based on both the Book Usage Data Provider Specifications and Data Recipient Specifications (SECTION II, Part I), it is noted that legal persons, such as public institutions, corporations, and not-for-profit organizations, were identified. There was no mention of natural persons in either set of specifications." 3- In Section II, Part II of the Communicating Data Quality through Transparent Trust Level Indicators, the addition of a quality assurance indicator is proposed. This indicator evaluates the Data Provider's measures to ensure accuracy, completeness (reliability of usage data), including validation processes, error detection, and correction mechanisms. No It's plainly a necessary document, one that is clear when read carefully. At the same time, it is dense and demanding. The main missing pieces are those that are specified as the future work of the technical committee. 												
<p>Overall, on a scale from 1 to 5 (where 1 is 'not clear at all' and 5 is 'very clear', how clear are the sections within the rulebook?</p>	<p>4 responses</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Clarity Rating Distribution</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Rating</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1 - not clear at all</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5 - very clear</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Rating	Percentage	1 - not clear at all	0%	2	0%	3	25%	4	50%	5 - very clear	25%
Rating	Percentage												
1 - not clear at all	0%												
2	0%												
3	25%												
4	50%												
5 - very clear	25%												
<p>Is there a particular section you find confusing and if so, what are your suggestions to improve it? You can list more than one section and multiple suggestions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Part 1 seems to have a lot of legal definitions not really relevant to this project. Could it be streamlined? For example, there's a section giving an example of where a health care professional might view data on behalf of a patient. That's surely not relevant to book usage data. N/A No, I found the writing lucid and concise (or as concise as it can be given the fairly complicated topics). No 												
<p>Please note anything else you'd like to share for consideration.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are there plans for the rulebook to be translated into other languages? Given that this is an international initiative I hope that other languages will be available. I recommend a plain-English summary at the top of each section. N/A 												

Rulebook Applicability

Free text questions asked for perceived challenges or proposed improvements for the document.

Questions	Answers
<p>Would there be any practical challenges to implementing the proposed rules in your own organization?</p> <p>If so, please describe what they are and offer any suggestions on how to address them.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No Limited resources within my organization may pose challenges in allocating sufficient resources to support implementation efforts. At this stage it is too early to say with certainty, but my impression is that the answer is No. The challenges are more likely to be administrative.
<p>Are there any resources that would help your own organization understand or apply this document?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A summary document No I don't know. Explanatory courses or webinars about the effort might be useful. A plain-English summary
<p>Please note anything else you'd like to share for consideration.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It's surprisingly long and convoluted. Anything that could be done to condense it would be helpful, if it's really to be a working rule book and not just a legal document. Excited for this work!

Privacy Concerns

On a 5-point Likert scale, respondents were asked to evaluate how well the rulebook addressed trust and privacy concerns. Three out of the four participants responded that the rulebook document draft addresses trust in the data exchange within the OAEBUDT model as well as privacy concerns as 'very well'.

Questions	Answers
<p>Overall, on a scale from 1 to 5 (where 1 is 'not enough' and 5 is 'very well'), how well does the rulebook address trust in the data exchange between public and private organizations within the OAEBUDT data space model?</p>	<p>4 answers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 - not enough 2 3 4 5 - very well Unsure
<p>Overall, on a scale from 1 to 5 (where 1 is 'not enough' and 5 is 'very well'), how well does the rulebook address privacy concerns related to the sharing of sensitive data within the OAEBUDT data space model?</p>	<p>4 answers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 - not enough 2 3 4 5 - very well Unsure

Conclusion

Community feedback provided from August 2023 to March 2024 directly informed the Rulebook Task Team's development of the OAEBUDT's Participant Rulebook. Complementing low web form engagement, focus groups generated valuable feedback for rulebook generation and validation. Edits made in response to the feedback provided herein were incorporated into the Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust.³

³ Drummond, C., Watson, J., Mounier, P., Elwell, J., Stern, N., Lenahan, J., Legre, Y., & Tsiavos, P. (2024). Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) (Version 0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11163158>